

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation.: This article shows that the development of artificial intelligence is one of the main urgent issues in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is aimed at systematic establishment of national scientific research and development activities in the field of artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence has been shown to increase the country's ability to develop a digital economy and innovate in every industry.

Key words: artificial intelligence, robot, sensor, thermal imager, space systems, digital economy, innovation.

In today's current times, digital technologies are rapidly entering all areas and people's lives from important topics. The development of the digital economy has become the most important task in our country. In the decision of the President of April 28, 2020 "On measures for the wide introduction of digital economy and electronic government" By 2023, the share of the digital economy in the country's gross domestic product has been set to increase by 2 times, the volume of services in this field by 3 times, and their export to reach 100 million US dollars.

Here, let's focus on the concept of digital economy. It is the optimization of the interrelated production, distribution, exchange, consumption and management processes (inter-human, inter-machine, cloud and big data) with the help of digital technologies and the Internet. is an activity aimed at making a large profit through

It should be noted here that the foundations of a new renaissance period - the third Renaissance - are being laid, which shows the greatness of our perspective. It is difficult to imagine the development of society and country without knowledge and enlightenment.

Digital economy includes complex innovative technologies:

1. Big data processing technologies - BIG DATA;
2. Artificial Intellect - Artificial Intellect;
3. Cloud technologies - Cloud Technologies;
4. Mobile technologies - e-mobile;
5. Internet of Things - Internet of Things;
6. Robotics and sensors;

7. 7. Digital electronic platforms and ecosystems;
8. 8. Quantum technologies;
9. 9. SMART-contracts;
10. 4.0 industrial technologies
11. Virtual and augmented reality technologies - Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality (VR, AR);
12. Crowd-sourcing and crowd-funding technologies;
13. Blockchain technologies;
14. Cryptocurrencies and ICO (Initial Coin Offering) technologies;
15. 3D, 4D technologies.
16. Drone technologies

It is necessary to update 60% of today's school and higher education institutions.

In order for us to join the ranks of developed countries, first of all, it is necessary to take the shortest path to advancement by acquiring knowledge in the field of advanced modern information and communication, Internet and digital technologies. At the same time, practical processes of digitalization of all sectors, including healthcare, cadastre, social protection, agriculture, and education, have begun in our country and will soon bring positive results.

The digital economy creates certain changes in society, in particular, its impact on working conditions is significant. In the conditions of digital transformation, the increase in automation processes, artificial intelligence, analytical systems working with huge data, and the increase in the use of robots serve as substitutes for labor resources. As a result, business conditions improve and efficiency increases significantly.

The most important thing in the purposeful introduction of digitization technologies into our daily life is that interactive communication with the people is accelerating by offering government services to the population. This also shows that it is the right way to further expand the system of providing electronic state services to the population and business entities based on the principles of "intellectual government".

First of all, digitization is a "data warehouse", a huge volume of data. Second, it is important for us to expand the various platforms to manage, store and process the flow of "big data". Thirdly, although the implementation mechanisms and sources of funding have been indicated in the implementation of these programs, we believe that it is important to strengthen public control during the monitoring process.

In the conditions of the digital economy, both the volume of GDP and the share of GDP per capita are high. The fact that the leader of our country pays attention to this issue at the national level has one goal, which is, first of all, to improve the living conditions of the population and obtain real incomes of the population.

The decision to adopt the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 2021 "Implementation of measures on the day of conditions for the rapid introduction of artificial intelligence technologies" was adopted. The purpose of this Decision is to rapidly introduce artificial intelligence technologies in accordance with the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy and their widespread use in selection, to ensure the quality of uploading and training from personal data, to improve skills in this field . favorable conditions are provided for personnel training.

With this decision, the list of pilot projects to be implemented in 2021-2022 on the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies was approved. In particular, artificial intelligence technologies are used in the following areas:

in the field of agriculture: monitoring the condition of soil and agricultural crops, as well as the operation of agricultural machinery, including combine harvesters, based on remote sensing data;

bank: production processing of the monitoring of tava commercial banks (creating, processing Face tava commercial banks)

financial insurance: to analyze and increase the amount of budget capacity, pension, social and payments, benefit payments;

transport: tracking traffic, controlling vehicles and driving vehicles in the process of driving transport locomotives;

keeping healthy computer: for early stage diagnosis of pneumonia based on the analysis of human lung tomography and breast cancer based on mammography;

in the field of e-government: for remote biometric identification of users (Face-ID) in the provision of e-government and financial services.

In today's conditions of rapid development of science and information and communication technologies, in the developed countries of the world, state and community management, economy, industry, social protection, education, medicine, employment, agriculture, defense, security, tourism and other fields Wide use of information and communication technologies and artificial intelligence remain key issues.

In Uzbekistan, by developing information and communication technologies and the digital economy, taking a place among the leading countries with innovative development by 2030 has been set as a priority.

In order to expand the use of artificial intelligence technologies, to improve the system of digital data collection, storage and processing, a number of works are currently being carried out in our country to train qualified personnel in this field, to support scientific projects in this direction.

In the framework of supporting scientific and technical research and innovative developments in the field of artificial intelligence, the total cost is 15.1 billion. 9 projects with a duration of 2021-2024 are being implemented.

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